

REAL-TIME PREDICTION AND DENOISING: DEEP LEARNING APPROACHES FOR NOISY TRAFFIC DATA

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Abstract

As urban transportation systems evolve, accurately predicting traffic states is crucial for efficient traffic management, enabling traffic managers to respond proactively to congestion. This study, conducted within the TANGENT H2020 project, explores data-driven methodologies for real-time journey time prediction in Greater Manchester. Data-driven approaches capture features in traffic data and leverage them to predict future traffic states. Focusing on deep learning methods, the research addresses the challenge of noisy journey time data caused by sensor limitations, such as inconsistent Bluetooth data capture and signal interference. Such problems contribute to noisy journey time data, shown by extreme fluctuations in the data. Proper denoising is necessary to produce reliable predictions. Various denoising techniques, including Wavelet and Butterworth filters, were tested with various parameters and methods (e.g., applying filters across both the entire dataset and within data windows). However, training the deep learning model on this denoised dataset and expecting it to work in production, isn't a suitable solution. This paper proposes a solution where the model simultaneously predicts journey times and performs real-time denoising. This approach improves the model's adaptability and robustness in noisy data environments. The resulting model was implemented and tested, with results showing significant improvements in prediction accuracy, contributing to more reliable traffic management systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traffic prediction is an important component of intelligent transportation systems, enabling cities to optimize traffic flow, reduce congestion, and improve urban mobility. Accurate prediction models rely heavily on the quality of the input data, as inconsistencies or noise can significantly reduce the model's performance (Sun et al. 2024; R. Li et al. 2023; Qin, C. Wu, and Hu 2024; Wen et al. 2023). Preprocessing techniques, such as filtering and denoising, play a vital role in improving data quality before it is fed into deep learning models. Previous research (X. Chen, H. Chen, et al. 2021; Harrou et al. 2024) demonstrated that Wavelet Transforms can significantly improve model accuracy by removing noise from raw data. However, deploying models in real-time applications introduces challenges. Many preprocessing techniques, while effective in offline settings, may not be feasible for real-time deployment.

The journey time dataset used in this study consists of time series data from multiple routes in Greater Manchester, representing the time it takes to travel between specific points. Data quality issues pose a significant challenge. First, the sensors check Bluetooth MAC addresses without distinguishing different transportation modes, which complicates the identification of vehicle speeds, especially on routes with low match counts. Additionally, the signal range of Bluetooth sensors decreases significantly in the presence of obstacles, leading to gaps in data reliability.

Such problems contribute to noisy journey time data, shown by extreme fluctuations in the data. Proper denoising is necessary to produce reliable predictions.

Real-time traffic forecasting models operate under time and computational constraints. Typically, these models receive a window of time series data ranging from 1 to 3 hours during both training and inference stages (Y. Li et al. 2017; Z. Wu et al. 2020). However, many preprocessing steps are often applied across entire datasets or long periods. Applying some of these denoising methods to signals of varying lengths may not retain the same characteristics.

In this work, we propose a solution that allows a model to learn how to perform denoising and predictions simultaneously, using raw time series data. This approach aims to overcome the limitations of traditional preprocessing methods, making the model more robust for real-time, short-segment applications.

We contribute the following in this paper:

- Detailed and quantitative comparison of the Wavelet and Butterworth filter applied on the whole series to the method of applying it to sections on 1 hour signals using a noisy dataset with several similarity measures such as Cosine similarity and others.
- Detailed and quantitative comparison of the current state of the art Deep Learning models to imitate wavelet transform denoising and butterworth filtering.
- Propose a custom training loop to train a model that performs denoising and predictions at the same time without imposing extra time and computational complexity in real time settings.

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- Compare the prediction model trained on the windowed filtered data against the proposed custom training loop.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section II, we discuss the challenges and limitations of current filtering and denoising techniques in traffic state prediction and highlight their real-time constraints and impact on prediction models. Section III describes the dataset used in this dataset, its characteristics and inherent data quality issues due to sensor limitations. In section IV, we present the underlying deep learning architecture employed for journey time prediction. Section V outlines the normal training procedure for deep learning models. Then shortcomings of the standard training procedure in real-time applications are thoroughly studies in Section VI. In Section VII, we introduce our proposed training procedure that enables the model to perform denoising and prediction simultaneously which enhances the adaptability and robustness in noisy datasets. Section VIII, describes the similarity measures and error metrics used in this study. In Section IX, we present and analyze the results of our experiments and compare our proposed methodology with traditional approaches. Finally, Section X concludes the paper by summarizing the key findings.

II. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT FILTERING AND DENOISING TECHNIQUES IN TRAFFIC STATE PREDICTION

Accurate traffic state prediction is essential for effective traffic management and urban mobility optimization. However, the quality of input data significantly influences the performance of predictive models. Traffic data, often collected from various sources such as Bluetooth devices, GPS trackers, and loop detectors are susceptible to various forms of noise and inconsistencies. These imperfections arise from factors like sensor malfunction, environmental interferences, and data transmissions errors, leading to erroneous fluctuations and missing values in the dataset.

To mitigate these issues, filtering and denoising techniques are employed as essential preprocessing steps. Filtering involves the removal of unwanted frequency components from the data, thereby smoothing out rapid fluctuations that do not represent the underlying traffic patterns. Denoising, on the other hand, focuses on eliminating random noise while preserving the integrity of the genuine traffic time series. Together, these processes enhance the signal-to-noise ratio that enables the prediction models to capture meaningful trends and make more accurate predictions.

Moreover, the implementation of these techniques often relies on window-based approaches, where the traffic data is segmented into smaller time frames or "windows." This segmentation is necessary for real-time applications, where predictions must be generated with low latency and continuously as new data arrives. Windowing methods allow for localized filtering and denoising, addressing short-term anomalies without the computational overhead of processing the entire dataset at once. However, this approach introduces its own set of challenges, such as edge effects and the difficulty of maintaining consistency across overlapping windows.

This section addresses the inherent challenges and limitations associated with current filtering and denoising methodologies in the context of traffic state prediction. By examining traditional techniques such as Least Mean Squares (LMS) adaptive filters, median filters, Wavelet transforms, and Butterworth filters, we highlight their sensitivities to window size, edge effects, and real-time applicability. Understanding these limitations is crucial for developing more robust and efficient predictive models.

A. Limitations of existing filtering techniques

Various filtering methods used in time series forecasting are sensitive to the context provided by the entire signal. For example:

- Least Mean Squares (LMS) adaptive filters adjust their coefficients based on the input signal

$$\mathbf{w}_{n+1} = \mathbf{w}_n + \mu \cdot (d_n - y_n) \cdot \mathbf{x}_n$$

where \mathbf{w}_n is the filter coefficient vector at step n , μ is the learning rate, d_n is the desired signal, y_n is the output signal, and \mathbf{x}_n is the input vector.

LMS filters rely on the temporal context provided by the entire signal to optimally adjust their coefficients. When applied to smaller segments, the lack of sufficient context can prevent the filter from converging to the optimal set of coefficients, resulting in suboptimal filtering and inconsistent results across segments (Gu et al. 2003).

- Similarly, nonlinear filters, such as median filters, are sensitive to sequence length:

$$y_t = \text{median}(x_{t-k}, \dots, x_t, \dots, x_{t+k})$$

where y_t is the filtered signal, and k is the size of the window centered at time t . Median filters operate by taking the median within a moving window and can remove noise spikes. However, they may also distort the signal in unpredictable ways, especially in smaller segments, because the median value may not accurately represent the overall trend or pattern in the larger signal (Borowski, Fried, and Imhoff 2013).

- Wavelet filters decompose a signal into different scales of detail, with each level corresponding to a specific frequency band and time resolution. Most common wavelet transforms use dyadic decomposition, where the signal is iteratively

split into two frequency bands. While wavelet filters has been effectively used in traffic time series applications (X. Chen, R. S. Gupta, and L. Gupta 2022), issues related to edge effects and short filtering windows have not been adequately addressed. For instance, (Han-Lin et al. 2009) discusses the boundary problem associated with wavelet transforms, noting that the finite length of the input signal leads to distorted decomposed values near the edges. They propose an algorithm to mitigate this issue. Furthermore, the study highlights that wavelet transform can lead to increased storage requirements due to the nature of the decomposition process. To address this limitation, we propose a method to avoid the storage problem by teaching the model to learn all the preprocessing procedures, including but not limited to the Wavelet transform. In another study (Matsusue, Hasegawa, and Sato 2007), the authors propose maximal overlap Haar wavelet transform to suppress boundary or edge effects to improve the prediction accuracy. Similarly, (Tang et al. 2020) highlights that traditional denoising algorithms, including wavelet transforms may suffer from shift sensitivity and potential distortion of the original data, especially near the signal edges, which can negatively affect prediction accuracy in traffic flow prediction models. However, most recent studies, particularly in deep learning applications, often overlook the edge effect problem.

- Butterworth filters are widely used for smoothing and noise reductions in signals. However, when applied to time series data that are divided in shorter segments, Butterworth filters can exhibit several limitations. Edge effects become significant in short segments because the filter required data beyond signal’s boundaries for accurate convolutions, which leads to distortions at the beginning and end of the filtered segments. Additionally, the filter can introduce phase distortion due to their non-linear phase response which can affect the timing and the shape of the features in the signal. This issue can become problematic in applications like traffic forecasting where timing is critical. Zero-phase filtering techniques can reduce phase distortions but these are not feasible in real-time applications as they require future data points. Furthermore, selecting appropriate filter parameters such as cutoff frequency and filter orders becomes challenging with short signal lengths as there is limited data to accurately represent the signal’s frequency content that can lead to suboptimal filtering and loss of important signal features.

Having discussed the inherent challenges and limitations of existing filtering techniques, this study mainly focuses on Wavelet denoising and Butterworth filtering methods. The following sections will explain the dataset characteristics, the underlying deep learning architecture, and the proposed training procedure that integrates denoising with real-time traffic prediction.

III. DATASET

A journey time dataset from the city of Manchester has been used in this study. Spanning from January to December 2022, the dataset records a total of 35040 timestamps that corresponds to 204 distinct predefined routes with a temporal resolution of 15 minutes. Bluetooth sensors were deployed in different parts of the city to capture the aforementioned journey times. These sensors detect and record devices by checking their MAC (Media Access Control) addresses that allows tracking of individual trips and the aggregation of travel time across different segments of the network. Figure 1 shows one of these predefined routes, spanning from the green marker (origin) to the red marker (destination).

Fig. 1: Predefined route captured by Bluetooth sensors in Manchester. This route spans from the green marker (origin) to the red marker (destination). Journey times are collected using sensors that track devices based on their MAC addresses.

These Bluetooth devices provide an affordable way to gain insights into the flow and efficiency of the transportation within the city. However, the dataset comes with its challenges. A primary issue lies in the potential misclassification of travel modes, that can lead to inaccuracies in distinguishing different types of transportation, such as buses, cars, bicycles, and pedestrians. This misclassification has a great effect on the reported travel time when the match count is low, e.g., during night time. Additionally, the range of the Bluetooth sensor is subject to the variations depending on the presence of physical obstacles and client devices. This can affect the consistency and reliability of data collection. These limitations must be considered when analyzing the dataset and designing prediction algorithms that depend on these kind of datasets. Figure 2 shows a sample time series that highlights the challenges with the misclassification of transport mode, combined with low match-count. The x-axis represents timestamps, while the y-axis denotes travel time in seconds.

Fig. 2: Time series plot showing travel time data collected from one of the routes in the dataset. The spike observed at midnight highlights one of the challenges in using Bluetooth sensors for transport analysis. The zero values in the plot represents missing data points. The missing points are usually the result of no Bluetooth devices passing the route in the aggregation period.

IV. UNDERLYING DEEP LEARNING ARCHITECTURE

In this study, we utilized the MTGNN (Multivariate Time Series Forecasting with Graph Neural Networks) deep learning architecture (Z. Wu et al. 2020) as our forecasting model. This model has been widely recognized in the literature for its reliability in traffic prediction tasks (Jiang and Luo 2022; Jin et al. 2024). Additionally, MTGNN exhibits robustness in managing noisy datasets, substantial amounts of missing data (Rahimiasl, Vanderhoydonc, and Mercelis 2024), and ability to learn the spatial dependencies of the road network even when it is not available. This makes it a great choice for many forecasting tasks in the mobility domain. This architecture integrates several key components to make accurate predictions:

- **Graph construction and adaptive Adjacency Matrix:** MTGNN propose a graph constructor module that dynamically constructs an adjacency matrix that represents the relationship between different road segments. This module is capable of utilizing predefined adjacency matrices, learning adaptive ones during training, or combining both approaches.
- **Mix-Hop Propagation:** The architecture incorporates mix-hop propagation module to aggregate information from multiple graph neighborhoods. By retaining a proportion of each node's original state and progressively integrating information from neighboring nodes up to a specified depth, this module effectively balances the incorporation of local traffic patterns with broader spatial dependencies. The mechanism effectively models traffic flows that are influenced by both immediate segments and more distant road segments.
- **Dilated Inception for Temporal Dependencies:** MTGNN employs Dilated Inception to effectively model temporal dependencies of traffic data. This module utilize multiple convolution kernels with varying dilation factors and kernel sizes. This enables the extraction of rich temporal features across different time scales. Dilated convolution expand the receptive field without a significant increase in computational complexity that allows the model to capture both short-term fluctuations and long-term trends in traffic patterns.
- **End-to-End learning:** The MTGNN model is designed for end-to-end training that seamlessly integrates convolutional layers, graph propagation, normalization, and non-linear activation functions into a unified model. This approach ensures that both spatial and temporal dependencies are jointly optimized during training which leads to a more accurate and robust traffic predictions.

MTGNN was selected for this study due to its architecture design, which is tailored to address the specific challenges associated with traffic prediction. Its specialized approach makes it a robust and reliable choice for tasks related to traffic forecasting.

Fig. 3: The architecture of MTGNN (Multivariate Time Series Forecasting with Graph Neural Networks) for time series prediction. The input layer incorporates historical and real-time time series data (e.g., travel time) as well as external features (e.g., weather), alongside spatial features represented by an adjacency matrix. This data is passed through the MTGNN architecture, which consists of a Graph Learning Layer followed by Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) layers and Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) layers. The output layer generates the predicted time series based on the learned spatial and temporal dependencies.

V. NORMAL TRAINING PROCEDURE

The sliding window methodology is a common approach used in training deep learning models for time series forecasting, such as traffic prediction tasks. This approach uses a fixed-size window of historical data to make predictions. The window moves across the time series in fixed steps and each window is used to generate predictions. Consider an example where the historical data has a length equal to 9 spanning from t_1 to t_9 , and input window size and output window size are both equal to 4.

In the first step, a window of historical data is selected to train the model, denoted as $[X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, X_{t_3}, X_{t_4}]$, where each X_t represent the value of the traffic data at a specific timestamp t . The model learns to predict the traffic for the next 4 timestamps, the predictions are denoted as $[\hat{X}_{t_5}, \hat{X}_{t_6}, \hat{X}_{t_7}, \hat{X}_{t_8}]$, where \hat{X}_t represents the predicted value for X_t .

The process can be represented as:

$$[\hat{X}_{t_5}, \hat{X}_{t_6}, \hat{X}_{t_7}, \hat{X}_{t_8}] = f([X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, X_{t_3}, X_{t_4}])$$

where f is the predictive model.

After making the first set of predictions for t_5 to t_8 , for the next step, the window moves forward by one timestamp (or another predefined step size or stride), shifting it to $[X_{t_2}, X_{t_3}, X_{t_4}, X_{t_5}]$, and the next set of predictions will be for t_6 to t_9 .

In general, the input window W at step n , with input window size of i , is represented by:

$$W_n = [X_{t_n}, X_{t_{n+1}}, X_{t_{n+2}}, \dots, X_{t_{n+i}}]$$

And the corresponding predictions with output window size of j are represented by:

$$[\hat{X}_{t_{n+i+1}}, \hat{X}_{t_{n+i+2}}, \hat{X}_{t_{n+i+3}}, \dots, \hat{X}_{t_{n+i+j}}] = f(W_n)$$

The sliding process continues over the entire time series, and after processing all available historical data, the window moves back to the first timestamp to start a new epoch. Multiple epochs are usually needed to optimize the model's parameter.

The main limitation of the standard training procedure is that the model's input and output come from the same time series (Kosma et al. 2022). This means that all preprocessing should occur on the historical raw time series data. Consequently, the model is trained on the denoised version of the time series. However, this approach is impractical for real-time applications, as it requires training all or a significant amount of historical data from the initial timestamp up to the current point for each prediction. Such an approach is computationally infeasible, as it demands extensive store and repeated expensive computations with every new predictions in the inference phase.

Fig. 4: A normal sliding window approach employed for training a deep learning traffic forecasting model. The model utilizes a historical time series of traffic data, with an input window of 4 time steps (t_1 to t_4), and generates predictions for the subsequent 4 time steps (t_5 to t_8). After producing predictions for the first window, the process advances by shifting the window to the next set of time steps (t_2 to t_5) as input, generating predictions for t_6 to t_9 . The model ingests two input windows (Input 1 and Input 2) sequentially from the historical time series, processes them, and outputs two corresponding predictions (Predictions 1 and Predictions 2). This iterative procedure continues until the model has processed all available historical data (completing one epoch), and is repeated over the required number of epochs to optimize the model's performance.

VI. REAL-TIME CONSTRAINTS OF THE NORMAL TRAINING PROCEDURES FOR WAVELET DENOISING AND BUTTERWORTH FILTER

A. Wavelet Denoising Procedure and real-time constraints

Wavelet denoising is an important technique in time series data preprocessing, which has been used in numerous studies of traffic predictions (Tamilselvi et al. 2024; Sun et al. 2024). By decomposing the signal (time series) into various components, wavelet denoising effectively isolates and suppresses noise while keeping the characteristics and patterns of the original data. This section explains the standard wavelet denoising procedure and examines its limitations in the real-time traffic prediction applications.

- Step 1: Data Decomposition

We begin by selecting an appropriate wavelet basis (e.g., Haar, Daubechies (db), Symlets (sym), etc.) and setting the decomposition level j . The signal $A(t)$ is decomposed into its approximation $B_j(t)$ and detail components $C_j(t)$ across multiple levels j using the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT):

$$A(t) = B_j(t) + \sum_{j=1}^J C_j(t)$$

where $B_j(t)$ represents the approximation at level j , and $C_j(t)$ represents the detail components.

- Step 2: Noise Estimation, Threshold Calculation, and Coefficient Modification

To reduce noise, we estimate the noise level σ using the Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) of the detail coefficients c_j :

$$\sigma = \frac{\text{med}(|c_j|)}{0.6745}$$

We then compute a universal threshold s_j for soft thresholding:

$$s_j = \sigma \sqrt{2 \ln(n)}$$

where n is the length of the signal $A(t)$. The modified coefficients \hat{c}_j are obtained by:

$$\hat{c}_j = \begin{cases} \text{sign}(c_j)(|c_j| - s_j), & \text{if } |c_j| > s_j \\ 0, & \text{if } |c_j| \leq s_j \end{cases}$$

- **Step 3: Signal Reconstruction**

After modifying the coefficients, the signal is reconstructed using the inverse wavelet transform. The reconstructed signal $\hat{A}(t)_{WT}$ is obtained by combining the thresholded detail coefficients \hat{c}_j and the approximation coefficients p_j :

$$\hat{A}(t)_{WT} = \sum_{m \in Z} p_j \phi_{j,m}(t) + \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{m \in Z} \hat{c}_j \Gamma_{j,m}(t)$$

Figure 5 shows an example of time series denoising using Daubechies 2 Level 4 wavelet using the procedure outlined above.

Fig. 5: Comparison of a raw travel time data (blue) with the denoised travel times using Wavelet Daubechies 2, with Decomposition Level 4, on a specific location. The x axis indicates the timestamp, and the y axis indicates the travel time. Missing values are represented as 0 in the blue lines.

This transform can suffer from edge effects at signal boundaries, which are challenging to manage in short segments. While these effects may be negligible or correctable in longer signals, they can pose significant problems in shorter segments. This is depicted in Figure 6.

Furthermore, the problem worsens in deep learning forecasting models due to the use of overlapping sliding windows with stride 1 during training and inference. For example, if the model's input size is 1 hour and the temporal resolution is 5 minutes, the inputs overlap by 55 minutes. A single timestamp change affects all overlapping timestamps due to changes in the input signal's characteristics to the Wavelet Transform. This variation may increase over time.

In Figure 7, we demonstrate the application of wavelet denoising using the Daubechies wavelet (db2) at level 2. The original signal, which has a length of 13, is randomly generated, and the wavelet transform is applied using the same

(a) This subfigure presents the denoising results for the entire signal. The noisy signal (gray) is compared to the windowed (red) and whole-signal (blue dashed) denoising approaches, as well as the clean signal (black dotted). The vertical green lines indicate window boundaries for the windowed denoising approach. The edge effects in the windowed denoising can be observed at these boundaries.

(b) This subfigure zooms into the beginning of the signal to highlight the edge effects introduced by the windowed denoising approach (red).

Fig. 6: Comparison of wavelet denoising approaches with windowed and whole signal processing. Wavelet-based denoising is applied to a noisy signal (time series) using two methods: windowed processing and whole-signal processing. The edge effects caused by windowing are examined, as they can introduce artifacts in shorter signal segments. The denoising performance of each approach is compared against the clean signal.

parameters to two overlapping sections of the signal. This approach shows the effect of denoising in real world applications and how it would corrupt the input time series to the prediction model.

Additionally, wavelet coefficients across different scales are interdependent, capturing information that spans significant portions of the signal. This interdependence can lead to misinterpretation when analyzing small segments, as the relationship between coefficients at different scales may not be fully captured. The multiresolution nature of wavelet transforms, advantageous for large signals, becomes a limitation when applied to smaller segments, as the transform may not fully exploit its ability to capture features at various scales.

B. Butterworth Filtering Procedure and real-time constraints

Butterworth filtering is a widely used technique in signal processing to remove noise from time series data while preserving the characteristics of the original signal. Unlike wavelet denoising which decomposes the signal into various frequency components, the Butterworth filter employs a frequency-domain approach to attenuate specific frequency bands associated with noise. This section explains the standard Butterworth filtering procedure and examines its limitations in the real-time traffic prediction applications.

- Step 1: Signal Preparation:

We start with the time series signal $A(t)$, sampled at a frequency f_s , which is determined by the temporal resolution of the data. In our case study, the data is recorded every 15 minutes, hence the sampling frequency is:

Fig. 7: Comparison of denoised overlapping windows and the entire time series. The plot shows the original time series (green dashed line) against two versions of the denoised time series: one computed over the interval from index 0 to 11 (orange line) and the other over the interval from index 1 to 12 (red line). This comparison shows how the choice of overlapping intervals can influence the results of the denoising process.

$$f_s = \frac{1}{15 \times 60 \text{seconds}} = 0.001111 \text{Hz}$$

- Step 2: Filter Design

A low-pass butterworth filter is designed to attenuate high-frequency noise while preserving the essential low-frequency components of the signal or time series. The design of the Butterworth filter involves specifying the cutoff frequency f_c and the filter order N . The cutoff frequency f_c is chosen based on the minimum period of fluctuations we aim to retain in the signal (e.g, variations longer than 4 hours).

The normalized cutoff frequency ω'_c is calculated as:

$$\omega'_c = \frac{f_c}{0.5f_s}$$

where $0.5f_s$ is the Nyquist frequency.

The magnitude response of the analog Butterworth filter is given by:

$$H(j\omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_c}\right)^{2N}}}$$

where $\omega = 2\pi f$ and $\omega_c = 2\pi f_c$ are the angular frequencies.

The transfer function $H(s)$ of the analog Butterworth filter in the s -domain is expressed as:

$$H(s) = \frac{\omega_c^N}{\prod_{k=1}^N (s - p_k)}$$

where p_k are the poles of the Butterworth filter on a circle in the left half of the complex s -plane, given by:

$$p_k = \omega_c e^{j\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\pi(2k-1)}{2N}\right)}, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$$

Expanding the denominator leads to a polynomial in s with coefficients a_i derived from the Butterworth polynomial.

For digital filter design, the bilinear transformation is applied to convert the analog filter into a digital one, resulting in the filter coefficients b and a . The digital Butterworth filter's transfer function $H(z)$ is expressed as:

$$H(z) = \frac{b_0 + b_1 z^{-1} + \dots + b_N z^{-N}}{1 + a_1 z^{-1} + \dots + a_N z^{-N}}$$

b and a coefficients are determined using numerical methods implemented in SciPy.

- Step 3: Zero-phase Filtering

To prevent phase distortion, the signal $A(t)$ is filtered using a zero-phase filtering method. This is achieved by applying the filter forward and then backward to cancel out any phase shift introduced during the filtering process (Gustafsson 1996). This process can be represented as:

$$B(t) = h(t) * A(t)$$

$$\hat{A}(t) = h(-t) * B(t)$$

where:

- $h(t)$ is the impulse response of the filter,
- $*$ denotes linear convolution,
- $B(t)$ is the intermediate filtered signal after the first pass of the filter,
- and $\hat{A}(t)$ is the zero-phased filtered signal.

This process effectively applies the filter in both forward and reverse directions that results in zero phase distortion and a magnitude response that is the square of the original filter's magnitude response. SciPy's implementation of this method has been used in this study (Virtanen et al. 2020).

The choice of filter parameters like cutoff frequency f_c and filter order N significantly affects the filter's performance. A lower cutoff frequency removes more high-frequency noise but risks attenuating important signal components. A higher filter order provides a sharper transition between the passband and stopband but can introduce numerical instability and increase computational complexity.

Edge effects are also a concern in Butterworth filter, as the filtering process can distort the signal at the boundaries due to the lack of data beyond signal's start and end points. The issue is intensified in short signal segments where the proportion of data affected by edge distortion is larger.

Moreover, applying zero-phase filtering in real-time systems is challenging because it requires future data points that are not yet available. This limitation makes such methods unsuitable for real-time applications.

To have a comprehensive analysis of the proposed methodology, six parameter sets were chosen (see Table I) and the proposed methodology and the baselines are applied on these parameter sets in Section IX.

Method	Sampling Frequency (Hz)	Cutoff Frequency (Hz)	Filter Order
PSet1	$1/(15 * 60) = 0.00111$	$1/(1 * 60 * 60)$	4
PSet2	$1/(15 * 60) = 0.00111$	$1/(1 * 60 * 60)$	8
PSet3	$1/(15 * 60) = 0.00111$	$1/(8 * 60 * 60)$	4
PSet4	$1/(15 * 60) = 0.00111$	$1/(8 * 60 * 60)$	8
PSet5	$1/(15 * 60) = 0.00111$	$1/(4 * 60 * 60)$	4
PSet6	$1/(15 * 60) = 0.00111$	$1/(4 * 60 * 60)$	8

TABLE I: Butterworth Filter Parameters for Different Parameter Sets (PSet1 to PSet6)

VII. PROPOSED TRAINING PROCEDURE

In this section, we propose a training procedure for the noisy datasets that enables the model to denoise the data and make predictions at the same time. This approach for training traffic prediction models uses both raw and processed historical time series data. In this process, two time series X and Z are used instead of only one time series. The X represents the raw data and Z represents the processed data. The processing of the data can be denoising, however, other processing steps can be included as well.

In the first step, similar to the normal procedure, a window of historical data is selected to train the model, denoted as $[X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, X_{t_3}, X_{t_4}]$, where each X_t represent the value of the traffic data at a specific timestamp t . The model learns to predict the traffic for the next 4 timestamps, but instead of learning to predict the traffic value using X , it learns to predict the traffic value using Z , denoted as $[\hat{Z}_{t_5}, \hat{Z}_{t_6}, \hat{Z}_{t_7}, \hat{Z}_{t_8}]$, where \hat{Z}_t represents the predicted value for Z_t .

This process can be represented as:

$$[\hat{Z}_{t_5}, \hat{Z}_{t_6}, \hat{Z}_{t_7}, \hat{Z}_{t_8}] = f([X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, X_{t_3}, X_{t_4}])$$

where f is the predictive model.

After making the first set of predictions for t_5 to t_8 , for the next step, the window moves forward by one (or another predefined step size) timestamp, shifting it to $[X_{t_2}, X_{t_3}, X_{t_4}, X_{t_5}]$, and the next set of predictions will be for t_6 to t_9 . The input window W at step n , with input window size of i , is the same as before and is represented by:

$$W_n = [X_{t_n}, X_{t_{n+1}}, X_{t_{n+2}}, \dots, X_{t_{n+i}}]$$

The corresponding predictions with output window size of j are represented by:

$$[\hat{Z}_{t_{n+i+1}}, \hat{Z}_{t_{n+i+2}}, \hat{Z}_{t_{n+i+3}}, \dots, \hat{Z}_{t_{n+i+j}}] = f(W_n)$$

The sliding process continues over the entire time series of X and Z , and after processing all available historical and processed data, the window moves back to the first timestamp to start a new epoch. Multiple epochs are usually needed to optimize the model's parameter. This process is depicted in figure 8. The proposed process is a simple modification on the sliding window approach which theoretically works with all the machine learning methodologies that use sliding window approaches.

Fig. 8: The proposed training procedure for noisy datasets, leveraging both raw and processed time series data. The raw historical time series (X) is shown at the top, with two windows of data (Input 1 and Input 2) extracted from it and fed to the predictive model. The processed historical time series (Z), shown at the bottom, is used to train the model by making predictions for processed values (Predictions 1 and Predictions 2). The model iteratively processes both input windows, predicting the next set of values in the processed time series. This sliding window approach enables the model to denoise the data and make predictions at the same time.

VIII. SIMILARITY MEASURES AND METRICS USED IN THIS STUDY

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed methodology, we quantify the performance using a range of similarity measures and error metrics. Specifically, we report the following four metrics: Normalized Euclidean similarity, Cosine similarity, Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The similarity measures provide insights into the geometric relationship between ground truth and predictions, while error metrics help assess the accuracy of the model by providing a numerical measure of the difference between predicted and observed values. These similarity measures are detailed further below.

- Normalized Euclidean Similarity

The Normalized Euclidean similarity measures the straight-line distance between two points in a multi-dimensional space. For two time series $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$ and $Y = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n)$, the Euclidean distance $d(X, Y)$ is given by:

$$d(X, Y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - Y_i)^2}$$

The Euclidean similarity $S_{\text{Euclidean}}$ can then be normalized as:

$$S_{\text{Euclidean}} = 1 - \frac{d(X, Y)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \max(X_i^2, Y_i^2)} + \epsilon}$$

where $\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \max(X_i^2, Y_i^2)}$ is the maximum possible distance and ϵ is a small positive constant to prevent division by zero.

- **Cosine Similarity**

Cosine similarity evaluates the cosine of the angle between two non-zero vectors. For two time series X and Y , the cosine similarity S_{Cosine} is given by:

$$S_{\text{Cosine}} = \frac{X \cdot Y}{\|X\| \|Y\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2}}$$

- **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)**

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is the square root of the Mean Squared Error. It is a popular metric for measuring the difference between values predicted by a model and the values observed. For two time series $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$ and $Y = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n)$, the RMSE is defined as:

$$\text{RMSE}(X, Y) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - Y_i)^2}$$

RMSE gives an idea of the magnitude of errors by providing the standard deviation of the prediction errors. A lower RMSE indicates better model performance.

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE)**

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is a widely used metric that quantifies the average magnitude of the errors in a set of predictions, without considering their direction. It measures the average absolute difference between the values predicted by a model and the actual observed values. Given two time series $X = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$ and $Y = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n)$, the MAE is defined as:

$$\text{MAE}(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |X_i - Y_i|$$

MAE provides an intuitive measure of prediction accuracy, as it directly reflects the average magnitude of the prediction errors. Unlike RMSE, it does not heavily penalize large errors, making it a more robust metric in the presence of outliers. A lower MAE value indicates better predictive performance, with the errors represented in the same unit as the original data.

IX. RESULTS

In this section, we present a comprehensive comparison of different denoising approaches applied to real-time traffic prediction, focusing on Wavelet denoising and Butterworth filtering methods. The proposed methodology involves training models that perform denoising and predictions simultaneously to improve the accuracy and applicability of prediction models. We conduct several experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of these methods, comparing window-based filtering to whole series filtering, and assessing the performance of deep learning models to mimic the filtering processes alone.

A. Comparison Between Window-Based Filtering and Whole Series Filtering

We first compare the performance of window-based filtering against whole series filtering for both Wavelet denoising and Butterworth filtering methodologies. In the window-based approach, the denoising algorithm is applied to non-overlapping windows of the dataset, each of length 12. This corresponds to simulating a real-time scenario. The whole series filtering applies the denoising algorithm to the entire dataset in a single operation serving as a benchmark for the comparison.

For the Wavelet denoising, we experimented with five different parameter settings with different wavelet type and decomposition levels. For the Butterworth filter, we used six different parameter sets defined in Table I where the parameters include filter order and cutoff frequencies.

The performance of these denoising and filtering methods was evaluated by calculating similarity metrics on the last 20% of the time series data. Tables II and III present the results for Wavelet denoising and Butterworth filtering methods, respectively.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
wavelet_db2_level_2	0.5555 ± 0.2461	0.8128 ± 0.2708	55.3163 ± 63.9029	31.641 ± 31.9603
wavelet_db2_level_3	0.5906 ± 0.2501	0.8295 ± 0.2698	52.6804 ± 61.2222	29.7278 ± 31.4433
wavelet_db2_level_4	0.6407 ± 0.2544	0.8518 ± 0.2697	46.6906 ± 57.2425	24.8036 ± 26.64
wavelet_db4_level_4	0.6483 ± 0.2616	0.8511 ± 0.2788	45.3546 ± 56.9418	24.9232 ± 27.9235
wavelet_db4_level_5	0.683 ± 0.2567	0.8692 ± 0.2761	41.0235 ± 51.1055	22.6866 ± 25.9223

TABLE II: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter settings of the windowed Wavelet denoising method to the whole series denoising across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the window based Wavelet denoising compared to the whole-series denoising. Each row represent a specific Wavelet configuration, identified by the Wavelet type and decomposition level. For example, wavelet_db2_level_2 indicates the use of a "db2" Wavelet transform at level 2 decomposition. A higher value indicates better alignment for Euclidean and Cosine similarities and lower values indicates better performance for RMSE and MAE.

The denoising effectiveness of the Wavelet denoising techniques employed in this study can be categorized in descending order as follows: wavelet_db4_level_5, wavelet_db4_level_4, wavelet_db2_level_4, wavelet_db2_level_3, and wavelet_db2_level_2. This ranking suggests that the db4 Wavelet outperforms the db2 Wavelet due to its higher number of vanishing moments, which are useful in capturing signal smoothness more effectively. Additionally, a higher decomposition level improves the separation of signal from noise. However, while increased decomposition level can enhance denoising, they do not offer infinite improvements, since beyond a certain level, the yields diminish and further decomposition may even lead to a performance degradation. However, this study does not exceed level where such diminishing returns or degradation effects are typically observed.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
PSet1	0.9025 ± 0.0665	0.9925 ± 0.0109	19.5823 ± 23.0887	7.3461 ± 9.1017
PSet2	0.8955 ± 0.0699	0.9914 ± 0.0122	21.2171 ± 25.0191	9.2694 ± 11.4319
PSet3	0.7764 ± 0.1323	0.9588 ± 0.0519	44.4648 ± 48.8705	24.25 ± 27.5844
PSet4	0.474 ± 0.2432	0.7626 ± 0.2138	124.8978 ± 126.671	70.7627 ± 73.8743
PSet5	0.8167 ± 0.1197	0.9719 ± 0.0414	36.2221 ± 40.8412	16.9544 ± 19.7357
PSet6	0.8275 ± 0.1	0.9769 ± 0.0267	33.4756 ± 36.5001	17.0163 ± 19.0395

TABLE III: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter sets (PSet1 to PSet6 detailed in Table I) of the windowed butterworth filter to the whole series filtering across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the window based butterworth filtering compared to the whole-series filtering. A higher value indicates better alignment for Euclidean and Cosine similarities and lower values indicates better performance for RMSE and MAE.

The results indicate the challenges of real-time filtering due to issues such as edge effects and other limitations discussed in this paper.

B. Comparison Between Deep Learning Filtering and Whole Series Filtering

We then trained deep learning models to perform denoising on raw input data with the aim to replicate the denoising effects achieved by the Wavelet and Butterworth filtering methods applied to the whole series. These models map raw input sequences to their denoised counterparts as obtained from whole series filtering. Although this comparison doesn't directly relate to our proposed methodology, it helps demonstrate the models' ability to handle the denoising task.

The performance of the deep learning model is compared to the whole series filtering results. Performance metrics are presented in Tables IV and V for Wavelet and Butterworth methods, respectively.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
wavelet_db2_level_2	0.7214 ± 0.2644	0.8353 ± 0.4404	21.1129 ± 22.3993	10.7144 ± 9.4872
wavelet_db2_level_3	0.7369 ± 0.2624	0.8826 ± 0.2917	22.4315 ± 23.8761	12.522 ± 10.5299
wavelet_db2_level_4	0.7554 ± 0.2639	0.8878 ± 0.2891	21.8879 ± 23.7992	12.4578 ± 11.0269
wavelet_db4_level_4	0.7602 ± 0.2661	0.8841 ± 0.3004	19.8331 ± 21.0796	11.9253 ± 10.9416
wavelet_db4_level_5	0.7565 ± 0.2671	0.8755 ± 0.3413	21.1139 ± 23.8114	12.9849 ± 12.873

TABLE IV: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter settings of the deep learning model that mimics Wavelet denoising method to the whole series filtering across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the deep learning model mimicking Wavelet denoising method compared to the whole-series denoising. Each row represent a specific Wavelet configuration, identified by the Wavelet type and decomposition level. For example, wavelet_db2_level_2 indicates the use of a "db2" Wavelet transform at level 2 decomposition. A higher value indicates better alignment for Euclidean and Cosine similarities and lower values indicates better performance for RMSE and MAE.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
PSet1	0.7739 ± 0.27	0.8867 ± 0.3006	24.5713 ± 29.2176	12.1813 ± 13.3467
PSet2	0.7714 ± 0.2691	0.8864 ± 0.3005	25.4629 ± 30.5144	12.7082 ± 14.3759
PSet3	0.7744 ± 0.2709	0.8864 ± 0.3007	22.1054 ± 24.2175	12.3964 ± 11.1056
PSet4	0.7694 ± 0.2697	0.8855 ± 0.3005	23.1286 ± 26.0099	12.899 ± 12.5956
PSet5	0.7726 ± 0.2694	0.8862 ± 0.3006	22.9295 ± 25.1622	12.5593 ± 12.2031
PSet6	0.7682 ± 0.2682	0.8854 ± 0.3004	23.5293 ± 25.8396	13.1823 ± 13.2565

TABLE V: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter sets (PSet1 to PSet6 detailed in I) of the deep learning model that mimics butterworth filter to the whole series filtering across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the deep learning model mimicking Butterworth filtering compared to the whole-series filtering.

Figure 9 provides a summary of the Wavelet denoising results, as detailed in Tables II and IV for the Wavelet denoising results. Similarly, Figure 10 summarizes the Butterworth filtering results presented in Tables III and V. The deep learning models demonstrate improved similarity metrics compared to window-based filtering methods for the Wavelet denoising approach, as well as for one of the Butterworth filtering parameter sets. However, in the remaining Butterworth configurations, the window-based methods outperform deep learning models. This suggests that deep learning models are effective at capturing complex denoising patterns, potentially surpassing simpler filtering techniques. Yet, for basic filtering tasks, such as those addressed by the Butterworth method, simpler approximation approaches can accurately manage edge effects and phase shifts, offering a sufficient and computationally efficient alternative.

Fig. 9: Comparison of deep learning-based filtering and window-based wavelet filtering relative to whole-series filtering. This figure summarizes the performance metrics of deep learning models trained to mimic wavelet denoising and traditional window-based wavelet filtering. The results, detailed in Tables II and IV, illustrate each method’s effectiveness in approximating whole-series wavelet filtering.

Fig. 10: Comparison of deep learning-based filtering and window-based Butterworth filtering relative to whole-series filtering. This figure presents a summary of the performance metrics for deep learning models trained to mimic the Butterworth filter and the traditional window-based Butterworth filtering. The results, detailed in Tables III and V, illustrate each method’s effectiveness in approximating whole-series Butterworth filtering.

C. Results of the Standard Training Procedure

Furthermore, we evaluated the performance of forecasting models trained on data processed using the window-based filtering methodology for both Wavelet denoising and Butterworth filtering. The predictions generated by these models are compared against the ground truth obtained from applying the filters on whole series. Tables VI and VII present the results for Wavelet and Butterworth methods, respectively.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
wavelet_db2_level_2	0.4893 ± 0.26	0.7557 ± 0.2989	64.8457 ± 76.8475	33.4343 ± 32.2771
wavelet_db2_level_3	0.5325 ± 0.2615	0.7759 ± 0.3035	63.4508 ± 70.398	32.9363 ± 29.9374
wavelet_db2_level_4	0.6021 ± 0.2705	0.8145 ± 0.3125	51.4408 ± 63.9882	24.6038 ± 25.2877
wavelet_db4_level_4	0.608 ± 0.2724	0.8201 ± 0.2982	51.0393 ± 65.0675	24.9958 ± 26.447
wavelet_db4_level_5	0.6326 ± 0.2697	0.8305 ± 0.3128	49.8706 ± 58.476	24.3287 ± 22.2137

TABLE VI: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter settings of the Wavelet denoising method across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the normal forecasting procedure compared to the whole-series denoising. Each row represent a specific Wavelet configuration, identified by the Wavelet type and decomposition level. For example, wavelet_db2_level_2 indicates the use of a ”db2” Wavelet transform at level 2 decomposition. A higher value indicates better alignment for Euclidean and Cosine similarities and lower values indicates better performance for RMSE and MAE.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
PSet1	0.4877 ± 0.26	0.7536 ± 0.2986	100.0694 ± 93.1783	57.7854 ± 49.7537
PSet2	0.4973 ± 0.259	0.7594 ± 0.2967	96.0526 ± 91.3625	54.0515 ± 44.9289
PSet3	0.5868 ± 0.2824	0.81 ± 0.2986	71.1485 ± 75.2005	43.1861 ± 40.5344
PSet4	0.4951 ± 0.2513	0.7605 ± 0.2894	90.3031 ± 80.289	59.753 ± 47.4723
PSet5	0.5478 ± 0.2773	0.7884 ± 0.3014	81.6605 ± 81.0125	48.9626 ± 45.4983
PSet6	0.5547 ± 0.2747	0.7911 ± 0.2991	80.4829 ± 77.5955	48.9282 ± 44.3209

TABLE VII: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter sets (PSet1 to PSet6 detailed in I) of the butterworth filter across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the normal forecasting procedure compared to the whole-series filtering.

The results presented in Tables VI and VII indicate a potential to improve the accuracy. In response, we introduce the outcomes of proposed methodology in the following section, showing its capability to enhance the performance through simultaneous denoising and prediction.

D. Evaluation of the Proposed Methodology

Finally, we assess the performance of our proposed methodology, where models are trained to perform denoising and prediction simultaneously in a real-time context. This approach allows for concurrent filtering and forecasting without the drawbacks associated with window-based filtering.

The results obtained from the proposed methodology are presented in Tables VIII and IX for Wavelet and Butterworth methods, respectively.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
wavelet_db2_level_2	0.5251 ± 0.2821	0.7603 ± 0.3612	55.3682 ± 76.4144	17.8663 ± 16.6841
wavelet_db2_level_3	0.5758 ± 0.2834	0.8052 ± 0.2989	53.2922 ± 71.2989	19.16 ± 16.18
wavelet_db2_level_4	0.6126 ± 0.2855	0.8236 ± 0.2963	49.901 ± 69.8681	17.7167 ± 15.5621
wavelet_db4_level_4	0.6205 ± 0.2934	0.8246 ± 0.2986	48.351 ± 71.2196	16.309 ± 15.2434
wavelet_db4_level_5	0.6371 ± 0.2973	0.8346 ± 0.3047	47.3885 ± 72.2706	16.2715 ± 15.6447

TABLE VIII: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter settings of the Wavelet denoising across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the proposed forecasting procedure compared to the whole-series denoising. Each row represent a specific Wavelet configuration, identified by the Wavelet type and decomposition level. For example, wavelet_db2_level_2 indicates the use of a "db2" Wavelet transform at level 2 decomposition. A higher value indicates better alignment for Euclidean and Cosine similarities and lower values indicates better performance for RMSE and MAE.

Method	Euclidean Similarity	Cosine Similarity	RMSE	MAE
PSet1	0.5108 ± 0.2524	0.7711 ± 0.2972	92.3184 ± 111.7058	44.9968 ± 45.2257
PSet2	0.5195 ± 0.2488	0.7791 ± 0.2972	84.7077 ± 99.731	39.5422 ± 38.9308
PSet3	0.617 ± 0.2817	0.8225 ± 0.3037	62.0311 ± 89.7883	30.3113 ± 38.5187
PSet4	0.6227 ± 0.2806	0.827 ± 0.3028	57.9993 ± 85.4817	27.4853 ± 33.9029
PSet5	0.582 ± 0.271	0.8091 ± 0.3007	68.6109 ± 83.7922	32.9424 ± 31.6977
PSet6	0.5811 ± 0.2691	0.8086 ± 0.3019	70.0052 ± 103.4461	33.7382 ± 45.616

TABLE IX: Performance metrics comparison for different parameter sets (PSet1 to PSet6 detailed in I) of the butterworth filter across multiple evaluation measures: Euclidean Similarity, Cosine Similarity, RMSE, and MAE. The comparison concerns the proposed forecasting procedure compared to the whole-series filtering.

Figure 11 illustrates a comparison between the proposed training procedure and the standard training approach for Wavelet, as detailed in Tables VI and VIII. Similarly, Figure 12 summarizes the application of the proposed methodology on the Butterworth filter. These results show that the proposed methodology consistently outperforms the standard forecasting approach across both Wavelet and Butterworth filters, demonstrating its effectiveness for real-time applications. Notably, the performance improvement is more pronounced in the Wavelet denoising process, suggesting that the proposed approach is particularly advantageous in scenarios involving more complex denoising requirements.

Fig. 11: Performance comparison between the proposed methodology and standard forecasting using wavelet denoising. This figure illustrates the effectiveness of simultaneously training models for denoising and forecasting in a real-time context versus the standard approach. The results correspond to those in Tables VI and VIII, highlighting improvements in prediction accuracy using the proposed method.

X. CONCLUSIONS

This study addressed the challenges of real-time traffic prediction using noisy journey time data collected from Bluetooth sensors in Greater Manchester. The inherent noise in the data coming from issues like misclassification of transport modes and signal range limitations highlight the need for effective real-time denoising techniques to improve the prediction accuracy and implement-ability.

We explored the limitations of traditional, but solid denoising methods such as Wavelet and Butterworth filters when applied in real-time settings. These methods often require processing a large portion of the dataset, which is impractical for real-time applications due to computation costs and issues like edge effects when applied to short data windows. Furthermore, solving the problems that arise from applying the denoising procedure on a window of time series instead of whole time series becomes more complex when multiple methods are combined.

We developed a novel training procedure that enables a deep learning model to perform simultaneous denoising and prediction. By training the model on raw time series on raw time series data and using the denoised data as targets, the model learns to denoise and forecast in a single step, without additional computational overhead during real-time inference.

Using the MTGNN architecture, known for robust forecasting, our proposed method outperforms traditional sliding window methods. Specifically, the model achieved higher similarity scores and lower error metrics compared to models using standard forecasting procedures.

Our experiments show that integrating denoising directly into the deep learning model enhances its ability to capture underlying traffic patterns despite the noisy data and real-time constraints. Specifically, the proposed methodology reduced MAE and RMSE by 60.14% and 10.01% for the Wavelet denoised time series and by 32.76% and 16.19% for the Butterworth

Fig. 12: Performance comparison between the proposed methodology and standard forecasting using Butterworth filtering. This figure illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed simultaneous denoising and forecasting approach compared to the standard forecasting procedure. The results, corresponding to Tables VII and IX, demonstrate the advantages of the proposed method in real-time traffic prediction scenarios.

filter. Even though the deep learning filter only models underperforms against window based approach in most of the Butterworth parameter sets. The proposed model increases the accuracy of the prediction compared to the normal procedure. This approach not only improves the prediction accuracy but also simplifies model deployment. This methodology is adaptable to other time series forecasting tasks where data quality is a significant challenge. The proposed methodology strengthens the integration of research and industry by enabling researchers to focus on enhancing data quality through denoising techniques applied to historical datasets. This approach allows for the development of these methodologies without concerns about their immediate applicability in real-time applications, where factors such as computational cost, latency constraints, contractual obligations, and privacy regulations may significantly influence the volume of data stored on the production servers.

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